

ProCleanLakes

Readme file

20250318-ProCleanLakes-

**Ecosystem, spatial and trophic
dimensions of niche partitioning
among freshwater fish predators**

Dynamics of a Top Predator-V01

**Funded by
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Reason(s) for data analysis: *Scientific publication investigating the effects of environmental variation on spatial and trophic niche overlap between two freshwater apex predators, the northern pike (*Esox lucius*) and the European catfish (*Silurus glanis*), in three different water bodies.*

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Used method(s):

Fine-scale acoustic telemetry to assess the spatial niche overlap of pike and catfish, analyzing their spatial and habitat use in relation to the thermocline and their presence in benthic versus open-water habitats.

Stable isotope analysis (SIA) to quantify trophic niche overlap and dietary differences between the species.

Habitat use, spatial niche width and overlap, and trophic differentiation were compared among waterbodies to determine how environmental conditions influence predator interactions.

Used software (incl. version and add-ons) and tools:

- *Locations of the individual fish were calculated using proprietary post-processing software UMAP v.1.4.3 (Lotek Wireless Inc., Newmarket, Canada). Filtering and further post-processing of fish locations are described in detail in Říha M, Gjelland K, Děd V, Eloranta AP, Rabaneda-Bueno R, Baktoft H, et al. Contrasting structural complexity differentiate hunting strategy in an ambush apex predator. *Sci Rep.* 2021;11:17472..*
- *To analyze habitat use in relation to species, waterbody, diel period, and their interactions, we applied a generalized linear mixed-effects model (GLMM) using the 'glmmTMB' package (Brooks ME, Kristensen K, van Benthem KJ, Magnusson A, Berg CW, Nielsen A, Skaug HJ, Mächler M, Bolker BM. glmmTMB balances speed and flexibility among packages for zero-inflated generalized linear mixed modeling. *R J.* 2017;9:378–400.).*
- *To visualize the modeled habitat use across different conditions, we used the plot_model() function from the sjPlot package (Lüdecke D. sjPlot: Data visualization for statistics in social science. *R Package Version* 2018, 2. 2024.).*
- *To evaluate species-specific habitat preferences across different lakes and diel periods, we performed pairwise contrasts using the emmeans package (Lenth Remmeans. Estimated Marginal Means, aka Least-Squares Means. *R package version* 1.10.3. 2024.).*

- To visualize the overlap of spatial (OL-SN) and trophic niche (OL-TN) between pike and catfish, we used the R package *rKIN* (Eckrich CA, Albeke SE, Flaherty EA, Bowyer RT, Ben-David M, *rKIN*. Kernel-based method for estimating isotopic niche size and overlap. *J Anim Ecol*. 2020;89:757–71.), which calculates the kernel utilization distributions (UD) for spatial and trophic niches. Kernel UD effectively reflects the asymmetric nature of fish distribution and provides a more realistic overlap than the commonly used ellipses. However, *rKIN* does not determine the uncertainty in the probability of overlap between species. To address this issue, we used the R package *nicheROVER* (Swanson HK, Lysy M, POver M, Stasko AD, Johnson JD, Reist JD. A new probabilistic method for quantifying *n*-dimensional ecological niches and niche overlap. *Ecology*. 2015;96:318–24.).
- The calculations of the predicted growth values for each waterbody and the pairwise comparison of growth were carried out with the *emmeans* package (Lenth Remmeans. Estimated Marginal Means, aka Least-Squares Means. R package version 1.10.3. 2024.).
- Data processing and statistical analysis were performed using R software version 4.4.1 (R Development Core Team R. R: a Language and environment for statistical computing. Team RDC, editor. R found. Stat. Comput. R Foundation for Statistical Computing; 2024.).

Data:

primary_data_telemetry.csv

- *species* – species identifier (pike, catfish)
- *lake* – lake identifier (name)
- *fishid* – individual fish identifier
- *timestamp_utc* – timestamp of fish location (UTC)
- *depth* – fish depth (m) at the time of location
- *bottom_depth* – bottom depth (m) at the fish location

thermocline_lakes.csv

- *lake* – lake identifier
- *date* – date of measurement
- *th_depth* – estimated thermocline depth (m), calculated as mean across all lake profiles

data_growth.csv

- *fishid* – individual fish identifier
- *lake* – lake identifier
- *tl_mm* – total length (mm) at first capture (catfish) or tagging (pike)
- *incred* – annual body length increment (mm)
- *age* – fish age in years (available only for pike)
- *species* – species identifier

Code:

NA

Additional files:

NA

License:

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Notes:

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